

EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES FILLED WITH CARBON BLACK AND CARBON NANOTUBES: HIGH VOLTAGE CORONA DISCHARGE STUDIES

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SUMMARY

The characteristics of the decay of the surface potential of corona-charged epoxy nanocomposites filled with mixtures of Carbon Black (CB) and Multi Wall Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) have been investigated. These materials show great potential for electronic device applications, such as organic field emitting displays, photovoltaic cells, highly sensitive strain sensors, electromagnetic interface materials, etc.

Keywords: Epoxy resin, Carbon Black, Carbon Nanotubes, Corona Discharge, nanocomposites.

ABSTRACT

Nanocomposites show different properties than the bulk polymer matrix because of the small size of the filler and the corresponding increase in their surface area. It is well known that the composite properties can change with the dispersion state, geometric shape, surface properties, particle size, and particle size distribution. Polymer nanocomposites based on Carbon Black (CB) and Multi Wall Carbon Nanotubes (MWCNTs) have been shown to undergo substantial improvements in mechanical, electrical and dielectric properties.

Specimens consisting of two types of conductive fillers (CB and MWCNTs), in different proportions, were dispersed in an epoxy matrix. Diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) with Triethylenetetramine (TETA) as hardener, was the matrix material, while different amounts of CB and amine modified MWCNTs were used as fillers. The procedure is fully presented elsewhere [1].

The electrostatic charge retained on the surface of a material influences the useful opportunities presented by static electricity, presented meanwhile some undesirable problems. This is manifest as the surface voltage created by the charge retained. The "suitability" of a material may be judged in terms of the maximum surface voltage created and/or by the time for which this is maintained [2,3]. The surface discharging effect of the nanocomposites are investigated using the John Chubb Instrumentation (JCI) 155v5 charge decay test unit. A high voltage corona discharge is used to deposit a patch of charge on the surface of the material to be used. A fast response electrostatic fieldmeter measures the voltage generated by the charge. From the measurements the "capacitance loading" experienced by the charge on the surface it easy to be calculated. This "capacitance loading" gives guidance to the maximum surface voltage likely to be

coated by certain quantities of charge on the surface [4]. A high capacitance loading means that only low surface voltage arise per unit of charge. Characteristic values calculated from the measurements are presented to the next Table 1 for CB and MWCNTs.

Table 1: Characteristic values

Positive charging	CB 1%	CNT 1%	0%
<i>RUN SETTINGS</i>			
Corona Voltage (Volts)	9000	9000	9000
Corona Time (Seconds)	0,0206	0,0186	0,0206
Surface Temperature (°C)	24,8	26,4	27,55
Surface R.H. (%)	32,87	41,58	39,86
Pretest (Voltage (Volts)	3,31	1,02	2142,01
<i>ANALYSIS RESULTS</i>			
Peak at (Volts)	288,67	90,373	2473,4
Analysis starts 0,1 secs after charging at (Volts)	146,01	63,908	-----
1/e reached after (Seconds)	9,775	492,52	7576
10% reached after (Seconds)	931,03	2164	21088
Received charge (nC)	457,47	1966,49	1,13242
Capacitance loading ()	680,506	9343,83	0,196599

As it is clearly shown there are similarities and differences due to the differences of the filler nature. A typical discharging behavior is observed in both systems (discharging rate increases linearly with filler content). The calculated conductivity increases with the filler content and reaches a plateau value in both systems (CB and MWCNTs). The large increase of conductivity in epoxy MWCNTs samples in comparison to epoxy/CB systems is attributed to the formation of a percolation structure [4,5], due to higher aspect ratio (length to diameter ratio) of MWCNTs, which is about of 1000, compared to 1 of CB. The next step in this research involves the investigation of discharging effects in epoxy nanocomposites filled with mixtures of CB and MWCNTs as filler.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was financially supported by the program “Archimedes II”.

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